

Review

Effects of Postnatal Care in Epigenetic Structure of Rodents

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Abstract:- This review summarizes the results of the previous studies examining the effects of the postnatal care in rodents. The maternal care in rodents is based on licking and grooming (LG) and arched back nursing. The studies are primarily focused on the LG related behaviour in the adult rodents. The alterations related to maternal care were observed in the neurobiological, endocrine, and behavioural systems of the rodents. The general results, in which High-LG pups grew up healthier, indicate that licking and grooming by mother has positive impacts on the offspring. It is proven by cross-fostering methods that licking and grooming frequency is not genetically inherited. Understanding the importance of maternal care in rodents, likewise other mammalians, can draw us a route for the same for humans. The main purpose of this review paper is to depict the significant results of the want of maternal care in rodents, and asserting the same importance in the same or different format for humans from rodents.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is proven that maternal care has various effects on one's mental health. Studies on mice showed that postnatal care during the first week after parturition affects the hippocampal epigenome via methylation and histone posttranslational modifications. (Lutz, 2014) Offsprings whose mothers engage less in licking-grooming (low-LG) show a higher tendency to stress compared with offsprings whose mothers engage more in licking-grooming (high-LG). It is for the benefit to mention that high-LG mothers often engage in licking-grooming twice as much as the low-LG mothers, with this difference only persisting for the first week. (Cameran et al., 2008) It has come to light that maternal LG has a high correlation with offspring's intelligence and physical development. Studies show that low-LG offsprings show decreased levels of neurophysiologic growth factors. These offsprings also show impaired performance on tests of spatial learning and memory. (Champagne, 2008) This paper focuses on reviewing experiments like the latter and imputing the results to view and discuss.

II. RESULTS OF PREVIOUS EXPERIMENTS

Cross fostering was experimented with to see the heritability of maternal LG. Offsprings of high-LG and low-LG mothers were crossed. When pups reached sexual maturity, their actions were examined. The results were that offspring of high-LG mothers who were nursed by low-LG mothers showed little LG and arched-back

nursing, while the offspring of low-LG but nursed by high-LG mothers showed high levels of LG and arched-back nursing. This experiment shows that maternal care is correlated with postnatal care, rather than genetic or prenatal factors.

DNA methylation is the addition of a methyl group in position 5' to a cytosine residue (5-mC). Especially when guanine is in pursuit of cytosine. (CpG dinucleotide) It is believed that this information is valuable for the readers who happen to do not know this interaction or happen to forget it. Offsprings of high-LG mothers show increased hippocampal GR expression, which helps have stronger negative feedback onto the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis (HPA axis). This causes mainly decreased reactivity to stress. (Lutz, 2014)

Poly(I:C) treatment at E12.5 alters maternal care behaviour (MCB): The experiment focused on pup licking/grooming (LG), nest-building, nursing, and non-relevant behaviour which were assessed for 4h per day. The statistical analysis demonstrated a significant decrease in the time poly(I:C) treated mothers spent in LG behaviour while they were more engaged in nest-building behaviour. The nursing and non-pup related behaviours showed no change.

In a series of experiments, handling was used as a type of manipulation where each pup was separated from the mother for up to 15 minutes for the first two weeks after the parturition. The results were that there was tenacious maternal care, high levels of LG, and arched-back nursing. (Branchi, 2009) During the first week of life, variations of maternal care can cause methylation in the genome and H3K9 acetylation of the NR3C1 promoter region in rats. (McGowan et al., 2011)

Upon gestational stress, high-LG mothers' behavior reversed back to the low-LG mother level. (Lutz, 2014) Offsprings reared by low-LG mothers show increased levels of ACTH, which has direct effects on reduced hippocampal glucocorticoid receptor (GR) mRNA. These are correlated hypothalamic corticotropin-releasing hormones. The release of this hormone activates the HPA axis and causes a negative feedback interaction with hippocampal glucocorticoid receptors through the stress response. (Champagne, 2008., Lutz, 2014)

Low LG offspring display a serious transcription decrease in 20 Pcdh of 33 genes registered within the Pcdh gene cluster. (McGowan, 2011)

Maternal care which is a group of actions is highly correlated with the endocrine biology during late gestation. Estrogen levels increase extremely, following the decrease of progesterone during the last days of gestation. These events are necessary for the setout of maternal behavior. Critical for the expression of maternal care, the effects of estrogen at the level of the medial preoptic area (MPOA) are of importance.

Central oxytocinergic systems affect the maternal behavior in rats via ovarian hormones. Estrogen increases oxytocin synthesis in the parvocellular neurons of the hypothalamus (PVN_h) that project to the MPOA as well as other brain regions that regulate maternal behavior. In the MPOA, oxytocin receptor gene expression and receptor binding are increased by the estrogen, which is mediated through estrogen receptor alpha. Intracerebroventricular (ICV) administration of oxytocin rapidly stimulates maternal behavior in virgin rats and MPOA plays a crucial role in this event.

Offspring of low-LG mothers were ovariectomized and exposed to high levels of estrogen, they did not have increased oxytocin receptor binding on the MPOA. (Champagne, 2008)

Even though maternal care affects the epigenetic programming for a short period of time after birth and those effects are highly stable and cause lifelong alteration in gene expression, it is, surprisingly, reversible. The reason for that is the definition of the steady-state methylation pattern by a dynamic equilibrium of methylation-demethylation reactions.

When the adult offspring of low LG-ABN maternal care is treated with TSA, the epigenetic marks on the GR exon 17 promoters is reversed; histone acetylation increased, the gene was demethylated and there was increased occupancy of the promoter with the transcription factor NGFI-A, resulting in increased GR exon 17 promoter expression. At this point, a behavioral change accompanies the epigenetic reversal so that there were no distinctive features between the stress response of the TSA treated adult offspring of low LG-ABN and the offspring of LG-ABN.

The neurobiological transgenerational effects of MIA on depression-like behaviour in the offspring brain, the modulated as targets of altered MCB and relevant for the pathogenesis of depression were examined. The hippocampus was primarily chosen because of its prominent role in the neural circuitry of depression. mRNA expression of MCR and GCR, both relevant to the pathophysiology of depression, was a significant increase in the hippocampus of F1 MIA compared to the control group. This situation was blatantly and statistically correlated with the amount of LG behaviour. These changes were also examined in the F2 generation. Statistical analysis showed a significantly increased

expression of MCR, but not of GCR.

The study conducted by McGowan, 2011 focused on the response to maternal care in high and low LG adult offspring. The increase and decrease of DNA methylation and H3K9 acetylation were detected throughout the entire epigenome with different distribution ratios. While clustered regions were showing strengthened responses, many sequences were showing no reaction at all. A significant 1413 probes of DNA methylation and 713 probes of H3K9 acetylation were found out of 44000 probes. (McGowan, 2011)

McGowan (2011) studied epigenetic changes in the NR3C1 gene. He defines a "regional difference" in DNA methylation and H3K9 acetylation as a difference of a minimum of 1000 bp (at least a probe per 1000 bp) difference between high LG and low LG adult offspring. Throughout the whole gene 723 RDme, (Regional Difference methylation) 373 being hypermethylated and 350 being hypomethylated was identified in high LG adult offspring compared to low LG adult offspring. He also defined 471 RDac, (Regional Difference acetylation) 204 of them being hyperacetylated and 267 of them being hypoacetylated. He discovered that these epigenetic changes were significantly localized within the locus with distances over 100 Kb. (McGowan, 2011)

III. DISCUSSION

The results of previous experiments clearly prove that the licking/grooming (maternal care) in rodents can result in behavioural and physiological alterations. Each study gives another perspective for us to understand these significant changes.

The results of the cross-fostering experiment is disproving the idea that postnatal maternal care is determined by genetic factors. It depicts that we are on the right way examining the results accordingly the licking/grooming situation of mothers in its postnatal period of them.

The increase in hippocampal GR expression in high-LG mothers in the next study and decreased reactivity to stress as a result of that shows how important the maternal care is for the stress activity in rodents. Considering the major results of increase in stress activity, we can understand how low maternal care damages pups.

The study including Poly(I:C) treatment is about the altering maternal care behaviour rather than results of LG. The poly(I:C) treatment in rodents results in decreased LG behaviour and increased nest-building; demonstrating that treating rodents with poly(I:C) (or increase in their poly(I:C) synthesis in their body) results in increased result activity in the pups.

In the late gestation, the increase of oestrogen and decrease of progesterone are important factors in maternal behaviour as given. We can figure out that any abnormalities in the late gestation will result in

abnormalities in maternal behaviour in postnatal period. The maternal care effects are stable, yet as shown in the study, they are reversible. The process lie behind this was given and it provides the harmful effects caused by methylation in rodents to be recovered. These studies show numerous results for rodents; however, how can we interpret those data for humans? Although maternal cares are in different version, it is that humans do not lick/groom their babies, as in rodents, the maternal care results in significant results in humans, too. Considering the fact that the alterations in stress related behaviour in rodents are caused by their physiological changes due to the maternal care, same physiological changes can be seen also in humans, even if not, other versions of it. The results show us the importance of maternal care in postnatal area in both rodents and humans, even if they have different physiology and behaviours.

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